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1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

Consonants:

--voiceless stops voiced after nasals; nasal reduced to a prenasalization feature ^mb, e.g.

[é^mboros] or omitted completely ([éboros]) (in some words of foreign origin, which have not been assimilated completely to the Greek phonological system, the sequences nasal + p do not give rise to [(m)b], esp. in speech of educated people)

--b, d & g after nasals or as result of the combination of a nasal + p, t or k, respectively

--velars palatalized before the front Vs /e/ and /i/ → k' (voiceless palatal plosive; also result of k + i, when the i is unstressed and a V follows: /kiólas/ > [k'ólas] 'already')

--m > [m̥] before labio-dental fricatives

--n has 3 allophones: [n] before all Vs; [ɲ] before /i/ or as result of combination of /n/ + /i/ + V, when /i/ is unstressed (dialect); [ŋ] before velar Cs (all allophones of /k, x, ɣ/)

--nasals preceding a C: (a) the nasal may become assimilated on place of articulation with the C; (b) it may voice a following voiceless stop; (c) it may disappear as a separate sound, but nasalize the previous V; or (d) it may disappear altogether

Vowels:

--all Vs remarkable pure in quality: V length is not a distinctive feature (fairly constant) → very little V weakening in unstressed (stressed Vs = unstressed Vs in quality of length; the chief component is extra loudness)

--an unstressed /i/ preceding a V is realized the following: (a) palatalization of a preceding velar C or of /l/ or /n/; (b) [j] if it is preceding by no C or by a voiced C (including /r/; (c) [ç] if preceded by a non-velar voiceless C in the same word

--the high Vs /i/ and /u/ (and sometimes /e/) are often reduced in unstressed position in fast speech

→ one of these Vs reduced before or after a voiceless C, it is devoiced

→ if a reduced /i/ or /e/ follows a velar C it may disappear and the velar is palatalized

Sequences of sounds:

--in traditional demotic certain constraints of possible sequences of sounds (irrespective of whether within words or across word boundaries:

(i) no instances of double C or V sounds;

(ii) in any sequence of of obstruents (i.e. stops and fricatives), all the Cs were either voiced or voiceless;

(iii) [i] could not occur before any other V (thus /i/ + V → [j] or [ç] + V); if the /i/ was originally stressed, the stress was transferred to the V;

(iv) two voiceless stops or two voiceless fricatives could not co-occur: such combinations were dissimilated to become voiceless fricative + voiceless stop (e.g. κτ or χθ → χτ [xt]; but not in *katharevousa!*); exceptions: the combinations σφ [sf] and [pt] in the apocopated preposition ἄπ followed by the definite article;

(v) a nasal could be followed only by a V or voiced stop; thus voiceless stops and voiced

fricatives were converted to voiced stops after a nasal, and nasals were deleted before voiceless fricatives (μπ & μβ → μπ [mb]);

(vi) a voiced fricative could not precede a nasal; here the fricative was deleted (γμ → μ [m])

⇒ numerous other sequences of sounds dropped out of the spoken language

⇒ influence of the *katharevousa* → many ancient or pseudo-ancient sequences of sounds entered the spoken language, even within the boundaries of the same word:

→ (i) double Vs /oo/ πρόοδος 'progress' ['proodos];

→ (ii) /ns/ ρύπανση 'pollution' ['ripansi] (this sequence, which is absent from Classical Greek, except across morpheme boundaries in compound words, also contravenes (v))

→ (iii) /io/

→ (iv) /kt/, /xθ/, /pt/, /fθ/, /fx/, /fs/, /sθ/, /sx/ and also some combinations of three sounds: a nasal followed by underlying /pt/, /kt/, /ps/, /ks/ or /ts/ (the first two only in words of non-demotic origin; voicing does normally not take place; the last three normally not voiced only when they stand at the beginning of a word after a preceding V)

→ (v) nasal + fricatives [f, x, θ; v γ, δ], the sibilants [s, z] and the liquids [l, r] (not all such combinations commonly within words!)

→ (vi) /γm/, /vm/

Diphthongs: V-sounds in sequence pronounced more or less as diphthong in words of demotic origin: greater stress on the first or second V, or both unstressed; the unstressed V(s) of a diphthong reduced in length; the second V most often [i] or [u]

Sequences of sounds within and across word- (and morpheme-) boundaries:

--in MG in principle no distinction between the pronunciation of sequences of sounds within words (or morphemes) and their pronunciation across boundaries (esp. the voicing of stops after nasals, the voicing of /s/ before a voiced C, the degemination of double Cs)

--many instances in which V-sounds may (or must) be deleted: deletion of /e/ in the preposition σέ before the definite article; the /u/ of the proclitic second person singular pronoun σου optionally deleted before a 3.person pronoun

--elision and prodelision are particularly frequent phenomena in MG when two V sounds meet at end and beginning of two words which are closely connected with each other semantically and syntactically

→ elision: deletion of a V at the end of a word, prodelision: deletion of initial V

-hierarchy of Vs: prevalence of one V over another: two identical Vs → degemination; two different → following sonority hierarchy: /a > o > u > e or i/

-stress is irrelevant to which V disappears, and also the order in which the Vs disappear

-elision/prodelision common in speech, but never obligatory

-prodelision never in adjectives or nouns (although with the numeral or indefinite article)

-prodelision of the augment in verbs extremely common, and also with certain other frequently used verb forms beginning with /e/ or /i/

--V-sequences across morpheme boundaries in compound words:

-in Classical Greek and in some varieties of *katharevousa*, hiatus between Vs in such circumstances was avoided by elision or crasis (the running together of two Vs to produce a third sound, e.g. πρό + ἔβαλα → προῦβαλα)

-while in traditional demotic similar phenomena occurred (mainly prodelision)

-nevertheless, there's the tendency to preserve the full form of each word in a compound, i.e. there are modern formations that do not follow the same rules, e.g. the rule which transforms a voiceless stop into a fricative before a V

--across word boundaries too there's a dual system operating on the sequences of Vs between ancient prepositions and their nouns or adjectives; e.g. *ὕπ' ἀνάπτυξιν (correct formation in Ancient Greek) for ὑπό ἀνάπτυξιν 'under development; developing'

--no word-final C-clusters (in traditional spoken Greek); majority of demotic Greek words end with an open syllable, i.e. a V

--only Cs in word-final position are /n/ and /s/ (but tendency in speech to avoid final /n/ by omitting or by adding an /e/ (e.g. [γράfun] 'they write' vs. formal [γράφun]); some words of *katharevousa* origin with final /r/ of C-clusters like /ks/; foreign loanwords may also contain word-final Cs and C-clusters

--word-initial position allows for any C and for a rich variety of C-clusters

--all clusters in initial position also in medial position

--2 and 3 C-clusters in initial position

--up to 4 C-clusters in medial position:

→ combinations of a voiceless plosive + /s/ or /r/

→ voiceless bilabial plosive or velar plosive + /l/ or /n/

→ voiceless dental plosive + /m/ (very rare)

→ labial nasal /m/ + dental nasal /n/

→ fricative + liquid /r,l/

--alternations of C-clusters: in traditional demotic no sequences of two plosives or two fricatives

--C or V length is not distinctive: stressed Vs may be slightly longer, but this is an allophonic (phonetic) and not a distinctive (phonemic) difference; when two identical Cs come together across morpheme boundaries, they are simplified to one (e.g. /sin-metoxí/ > assimilation of [n] /sim-metox'í/ > simplification of [mm] /simetox'í/ 'participation')

2. "Rules" Part 1

Assimilation:

--assimilation in point of articulation: nasals assimilate in point of articulation with the C that follows (e.g. /ton patéra/ > [to(m)batéra] 'the father'); also observed across morpheme boundaries in prefixation and compounding (e.g. /sin-pono/ > [si(m)bonó] 'I pity')

--assimilation in voice: (i) the voicing of a plosive after a nasal and (ii) the voicing of a segment (other than a nasal or a liquid) if it is followed by any voiced C including a nasal or a liquid (e.g. ton tímisan/ > [to(n)dímisan] 'they honoured him', in compounds: /sin-kátikos/ > [si(ŋ)gátikos] 'flat-mate')

→ the assimilation rules apply across derivational and inflectional affixes and between words forming a p-word or -phrase

Dissimilation:

There is a constraint on C-clusters within and between morphemes, which says clusters with two voiceless fricatives or two plosives are disallowed (but only for vocabulary following the demotic pattern); also effects in the inflection of verbs

--a fricative (not including nasals or liquids) becomes plosive if it is adjacent to an /s/, irrespective of the order of the two elements (e.g. /θa tréx-s-o/ > [θa trékso] 'I will run')

--if the C-cluster does not contain an /s/, then it is the order that determines which of the Cs will be the plosive and which one will be the fricative: the first of the two must be the fricative while the second will be the plosive, i.e. in clusters of two fricatives, the second becomes a plosive, and in clusters of two plosives, the first becomes a fricative (e.g. /pléx-θ-

ike/ > [pléxtik'e] 'I was knitted') !this rule is restricted to words of demotic origin, words of more formal or scientific style deriving from *katharevousa* do not undergo this rule!, it is also restricted to inflection, while derivation, such as prepositional prefixation, does not seem to be affected!

--in clusters with a plosive before a fricative, the initial plosive will change to a fricative, while the following fricative will become a plosive (e.g. /líp-θ-ike/ > [líf-t-ik'e] 'was lacking')

Deletion:

-C-deletion:

(a) sequence of identical Cs within a word or phrase, one C deleted (e.g. /mas sóstate/ > [masósate] 'you saved us')

(b) nasal deleted before liquid /l,r/ (e.g. /sin-roí/ > [siroí] 'large crowd')

(c) final /n/ of prefix /sin-/ deleted before a strident /s,z/, but final /n/ of prefix /en-/ not in similar circumstances (e.g. /sin-sítio/ > [sisítio] 'communal meal', but /én-simo/ > [énsimo] 'official stamp')

(d) verb-root final /n/ in verbs deletes before /s/ and /θ/ of perfective (e.g. /θα δέν-s-o/ > [θα δέso] 'I will tie')

(e) final /n/ of feminine acc. deg. art. /tin/ deleted before a fricative including /s/ and /z/ of a liquid /l/ or /r/, but the final /n/ of masc. def. art. /ton/ only optionally deleted, and final nasal of masc. weak pronoun not deleted before fric. or liquid of the following verb (e.g. /tin lípi/ > [tilípi] 'the sorrow' vs. /ton φίlo/ > [tonfílo] or [to φίlo] 'the friend')

(f) /θ/ and /ð/ in root-final position of verbs deleted before perfective marker /s/ (e.g. /θα pláθ-s-o/ > [θα pláso] 'I will knead')

-V-deletion:

--within words unstressed /i/ or /u/ adjacent to another V reduced to non-syllabic [j] or [w]

--in other combinations the Vs remain fully syllabic → hiatus, i.e. the combination of 2 Vs not avoided within simple words

--between morphemes within a complex word or p-word/-phrase, 2 Vs become together, one will be deleted

→ position of Vs in sonority hierarchy a > o > u > e/i (the more sonorant a segment, the less likely it is to be deleted; e.g. /ta ípa/ > [tápa] 'I said it') [such deletions esp. across boundaries between weak pronouns and following verbs; in demotic system deletion optional]

--V-deletion obligatory in derivational processes, esp. prepositional prefixation; sonority hierarchy not operative, instead rule: last V of the prefix is deleted (e.g. /para-édosa/ > [parédosa] 'I delivered')

--deletion very rare in combinations of articles + noun/adjective; but when → sonority hierarchy

→ deletion avoided when first V one of the definite articles ο, η or οι

--some prepositions lose their final V when preceding the definite article (σε 'at', απο 'from', and the adverb μέσα 'inside')

e.g. /se to trapézi/ > [sto trapézi] 'at the table'

! but: /mésa se tin póli/ > [mesti(m)bóli] or [mesasti(m)bóli] 'in the city' → two V-deletions and two assimilations (final nasal /n/ assimilates in point of articulation with bilabial plosive /p/ and this in turn assimilates in voice with the nasal);

! /apó tin eláða/ > [aptineláða] or [apotineláða] 'from Greece' → two-plosive cluster /pt/ created by deletion of final /o/ does not undergo the dissimilation rule which demands that the first C must be a fricative!

--final /e/ of sing. imperative verb may be deleted if followed by a weak pronoun with initial /t/: /páre to/ > [párto] 'take it', /kópse to/ > [kópsto] 'cut it' (this deletion normal with imperatives stressed on penultimate only)

--/e/ of penultimate syllable of the imperative plural forms also deleted after /s, r, l/: /párete ta/ > [párteta] 'take these'

--unstressed initial /e/ of personal pronouns and of adverbs εδω 'here' and εκει 'there' optionally deleted if preceded word ends in an V: /éla esí/ > [elasí] 'you come (imperative)'

3. "Rules" Part 2

DEFAULT SYLLABLE TEMPLATE:

--minimal VC or CV (V? e.g. [epérx'ete] → epér.x'e.te vs. e.pér.x'e.te?)

--CCV, CVC, CVV [paraéfaya] → pa.raé.fa.ɣa vs. pa.ra. éfa.ɣa?

--CCVC (=word/phonological free unit)

→ also word-initial + CV [θa trékso] → trék.so vs. tré.kso?

--article + noun/adjective → rarely V-deletion: [oalékos], [iexθrí]

STRESS:

-stress within a single g-word:

--stress is distinctive, thus words may be differentiated simply by the position of the stress (e.g. [píra] 'experience' vs. [pirá] 'fire')

--position of the stress within a word is not predictable, some general rules:

(a) disyllabic or polysyllabic word and some monosyllabic ones must contain one stressed syllable.

(b) *The antepenultimate rule:* the stress may not fall further from the end than the antepenultimate. it may fall on the last syllable (the ultimate), or the one before the last (penultimate) or the third syllable from the end (antepenultimate).

--position of stress remains constant only in a noninflected word such as a preposition or an adverb; in nouns, adjectives and verbs the position of the stress is affected by phonological and/or morphological factors

-phonologically motivated stress variations:

-nouns:

--stressed final, penultimate or antepenultimate

--in certain classes of nouns with penultimate/antepen., stress will move one syllable to the right in following circumstances:

(a) antepen. stressed nouns move stress on penult. syllable if an inflectional ending adds an extra syllable → *antepen. stress rule!*;

(b) antepen. stressed nouns became penult. before the genitive sing. ending -ου, the gen. pl. -ων, the acc. pl. -ους and the nom. and acc. ending -εις, in spite of the fact that no extra syllable is added (historical explanation)

-adjectives:

--**columnar stress**, i.e. keep stress in its basic position throughout the paradigm

-verbs:

--stress may move either to the left or to the right in cases where the inflectional ending has added syllables and the basic stress position violates the antepenultimate rule

-stress within a p-word:

--p-word = a domain in which may appear more than one stress: a basic stress and a derived

one → *enclisis of stress*:

(a) if a g-word is stressed on the antepen. and followed by a weak personal pronoun, which belongs syntactically to the same phrase, a second stress must be placed on the last syllable of the first word (e.g. [o jítonáz mas] 'our neighbour')

(b) if a verb in the imperative is stressed on the penult. and followed by 2 weak pronouns, a stress must be placed on the pronoun nearer to the verb (e.g. [fére mú ta] 'bring them to me')

(c) if a gerund stressed on the antepen. is followed by one or two weak pronouns a secondary stress will be placed on the last V of the gerund (e.g. [γράfondás mu] 'writing to me')

--phenomenon of enclisis is motivated by the antepen. rule; more than three unstressed syllables violate it, there must be stress on one of the last three syllables of the word: within a single g-word basic stress moves to the right; within p-words a second stress on the second syllable to the right of the syllable with the basic stress is added (the second stress, the stress derived by enclisis, is stronger!)

INTONATION: (Waring (1976))

--three basic pitch levels (high, mid, low)

--four basic tones (fall, rise, rise-fall, and fall-rise), and in addition a special raised fall (fall to mid-pitch)

--most common neutral intonation patterns are the rise at the end of a clause which is not the end of a complete utterance

--normally a change of pitch takes place (or begins) on a stressed syllable

--however, if there is to be a fall-rise or rise-fall, the second element of each may occur (or begin) on an unstressed syllable

--don't change meaning of word, only intonation of utterance/clause

4. Morpho-Syntax

Minimality/Maximality:

--high inflectional language: maximality?

--minimal size of phonological free unit: some monosyllabics of the forms: CVC [bój] 'height', CCVC [xtes] 'yesterday', and bisyllabics of the form: VC.CV [eftá] 'seven'

Reduplication:

--reduplication sometimes occurs in the passive perfect participles of certain verbs

--it is not applied to all verbs but is a learned feature, inherited from *katharevousa* and restricted to certain verbs, some of them having acquired a distinct meaning or function as adjectives

--reduplication rules:

(a) verb stems which begin with one of the Cs β, γ, δ, κ, λ, μ, ν, π, σ, or τ are prefixed with an additional syllable consisting of the same C + ε; e.g. βεβιασμενος 'forced, hasty' (from βιαζω)

(b) verb stems which begin with θ, φ, or χ are prefixed with τ, π, or κ respectively + ε, e.g. τεθλιμμενος 'distressed' (from θλιω)

(c) verb stems which begin with ζ, ρ, or ψ, or with σ + one or more other Cs, are prefixed with ε, e.g. εσκεμμμενος 'deliberate' (from σκεπτομαι)

(d) verb stems which begin with one of the Vs α, ε, or αι replace the V with η, e.g. ηνωμενος 'united' (from ενωνω)

(e) when the verb has a prepositional prefix, the reduplication (in accordance with the above rules) comes immediately before the verb stem, e.g. αποδεδειγμενος 'proven' (from αποδεικνυω)

(f) finally, some irregular examples: επανειλημμενος 'repeated' (from επαναλαμβανω),

κατειλημμενος 'occupied' (from καταλαμβάνω)

Inflectional Morphology:

- main stem of nouns always invariable, whereas some verbs alter theirs
- stress can be raised on the conjugation of verbs (i.e. it moves towards the beginning of the word), but can only be lowered in the declension of nouns
- most verbs dozen different forms → inflected for person, number, tense, aspect, voice and mood
- other means of expressing tense and mood: mainly periphrases, involving a particle or an auxiliary verb

NOUN-CLASSES:

- three noun classes
- masculine nouns of class 1 in nominative sing. consists of stem + thematic V (any V except ο) + -s
- feminine nouns: stem + thematic V (any V)
- singular inflection simply entails dropping or adding final -s
- three further factors:
 - (i) most class 1 nouns add the plural endings directly to the stem, while others add an epenthetic -δ- to the thematic V, and then the ending: parisyllabic vs. imparisyllabic
 - (ii) stress: in parisyllabics the stress of nom. sing. is preserved on the same V throughout the sing. in all class 1 nouns, and in all plural cases except the gen.; the same is true of the imparisyllabics, with the exceptions of the proparoxytones, which transfer the stress to the antepenultimate V in the plural → gen. plural of the parisyllabic most problematic
 - while proparoxytones in -as lower the stress to the penultimate in this case, nouns in -ίας and -ίστας, together with disyllabic paroxytones, lower it to the final syllable
 - the feminines in -i which possess a genitive plural stress the final syllable in that case, while feminines in -a are divided in between those with penultimate stress and those with final stress in the gen. pl. → most of the proparoxytones except those in -ότιτα have final stress here (those which do not do so stress the penultimate), as do all those with stems ending in a V, and all disyllables (large number of feminines in -a have no gen. pl. at all)
 - (iii) there is a category of masculines in -as and -is and feminines in -i which have different plural endings from the rest of the Class 1 nouns
 - the masculines end in -έας or -ίς in the nom. sg. and form their plural in -ίς (nom., voc., acc.) and -έων / -όν (gen.) (stress is on the syllable following the stem throughout)
 - feminines most of which end in -σι in nom. sg. replace the -i with the same endings as the masculines in the plural (-is and -eon), except the stress always falls on the syllable of the stem

STEMS AND ENDINGS:

- most of verbs have three stems (some of the stem changes follow certain predictable patterns)
 - e.g. πληρώνω 'I pay' → imperfective stem πληρων- + 1.p.sg. present -ω
 - simple past active voice: πλήρωσα 'I paid' → stem πληρωσ- + personal ending -α
 - simple past passive voice: πληρώθηκα 'I was paid' → stem πληρωθ- + appropriate ending -ηκα (actually made up of affix -ηκ- and ending -α, the latter indicating 1.p.sg.past)
 - ⇒ different personal endings for different tenses
- aspect: imperfective/perfective:
 - imperfective and simple past + augment-prefix, the syllable ε- → this augment

normally used with verbs that have an one-syllable stem beginning with a C and a one-syllable ending; the augment carries stress!

→ augment normally only in forms of the two active pasts: imperfective and simple past

--two futures formed periphrastically, i.e. they consist of a two-word phrase rather than a single word

→ both periphrases employ the particle $\theta\alpha$

→ e.g. imperfective future = particle + present: $\theta\alpha$ γράφω 'I shall write [repeatedly or habitually]' or 'I shall be writing [when sth. else happens]'

→ e.g. perfective future = particle + dependent: $\theta\alpha$ γράψω 'I shall write'

→ dependent: perfective stem + non-past ending → 'aorist subjunctive' or 'perfective non-past'; cannot normally exist independent of either a particle (like $\theta\alpha$, $\mu\eta(\nu)$, $\nu\alpha$, or $\alpha\varsigma$) or certain conjunctions

(→ table page 111)

--perfect tenses use 'to have' as an AUX, $\acute{\epsilon}\chi\omega$ 'I have', which also exists as a verb in its own right (present, past and future tables on p.112)

-AUX is conjugated to indicate person + non-finite which remains unchanged

--irregularities in the formation of verbal stems:

(a) change of radical V; (b) change of stem-final C; (c) deletion or addition of a sound or sounds; (d) metathesis of sounds; (e) *suppletion* of one root by another; and (f) lack of dental in the perfective passive stem.

→ up to three irregularities may coexist within the paradigm of a single verb

SUMMARY OF VERB ENDINGS:

--system of endings for the various tenses and moods: three preliminary remarks:

(i) verbs fall into two main categories (or conjugations): first conjugation or paroxytone and second conjugation or oxytone

-this distinction is based on the position of stress in 1.p.sg. of present active ("dictionary form"): 'oxytone' = 'stressed on last syllable', 'paroxytone' = 'penultimate stress'

→ verbs of the first conjugation are stressed on last syllable of the stem, i.e.

penultimate syllable of the 1.p.sg. present tense ⇒ 'stem-stressed'

→ verbs of the second conj. are stressed on the final syllable of the 1.p.sg., i.e. on the

ending rather than the stem ⇒ 'ending-stressed'

-second-conjugation verbs subdivided into two types according to the system of Vs which characterize their ending:

A: e.g. 1.p. αγαπῶ / 2.p. αγαπάς / 3.p. αγαπάει

B: θεωρῶ / θεωρεῖς / θεωρεῖ

(ii) endings added to either imperfective or perfective stem

(iii) many alternative forms within the verb system (variety sometimes regional/dialectal, differences of register or idiolect of speaker/writer)

→ p.117 table of verb endings

STRESS:

--stress of past and non-past forms of the verb → somewhat different rules

--in *past forms* stress follows the antepen. rule, i.e. it retreats to the antepen. syllable or falls on the first syllable in the case of a two-syllable form

→ two exceptions:

(i) in the active imperfect of second-conjugation verbs the stress always falls on the affix syllable -ούσ- (e.g. μιλούσε 's/he was talking')

(ii) in the passive imperfect the stress falls on the first syllable of the ending, except that in the third person plural of first-conjugation verbs it falls on the antepen. (e.g. ἐρχόταν 's/he was coming')

--in the *active non-past forms* (present and dependent) the stress falls on the last syllable of the appropriate stem, except for the present forms of second-conjugation verbs which are stressed on the first syllable of the ending (e.g. διαβάζουν 'they read/are reading')

--in the *passive present forms* of the first conjugation the stress falls on the antepen., while in second-conjugation verbs the stress falls on the first syllable of the ending (e.g. διαβάζεται 'it is (being)read')

--the *passive dependent forms* are always stressed on the first syllable of the ending (e.g. θα δοθεί 'it will be given')

--special mention must be made of verbs which have two adjacent Vs in the last syllable(s) of their imperfective stem, of which the first is /i/ → pronounced as the V [i] or becomes [j]; affects the position of stress in the active imperfect and simple past:

-the [j] is not counted as a syllable and therefore the stress, if it would normally fall there, retreats to the preceding syllable; this factor also determines whether a verb with a monosyllabic stem takes the augment (e.g. διώχνω [djóχno] 'I chase away, expel' goes to έδιωχνα [édjoxna] (imperf.) and έδιωξα [édjoksa] (simple past), both with augment)

-in other cases the two Vs retain their syllabic value (e.g. σχεδιάζω [s'xediázo] 'I plan', σχεδιάζα [sx'ediáza] (imperf.), σχεδίασα [sx'ediása] (s.past)), while a few verbs have imperfect and simple past forms of both types

--AUGMENT: involves a change to the beginning of the verb stem when the verb is in a past tense. If the verb stem begins with a C an additional syllable ε- is prefixed to the stem (*syllabic augment*). If the stem begins with a V, the V undergoes a change, traditionally described as lengthening (*vocalic augment*). (In Ancient Greek all past tenses of verbs had augmentation as a regular morphological feature.) In Modern Greek augmentation, when it occurs, can be divided into the following three categories: (i) syllabic augment, which is obligatory when it carries the stress in past tense forms, (ii) vocalic augment in a restricted number of verbs; and (iii) *internal augment*, which can be vocalic or syllabic, in verbs which have a prepositional prefix.

Syllabic Augment:

--only in past tense verb forms with a stem beginning with a C

--obligatory when the verb form consists of a one-syllable stem and a one-syllable ending and consequently (because of the antepenultimate rule) the augment carries the stress (e.g. έ-γραψ-α 'I wrote' (simple past), έ-γραφ-εσ 'you (sg.) were writing/used to write' (imperfect))

--when the verb stem consists of more than one syllable the augment is not normally used

--similarly, when a verb with a one-syllable stem has an ending of more than one syllable, the augment is not normally used

⇒ thus, the augment is only obligatory in the active past tense forms (imperfect and simple past) of first conjugation verbs with a one-syllable stem, when they are in the singular or in the 3rd person plural with the ending -αv

--a small number of verbs which have a simple past with a one-syllable stem but do not have an augment

--syllabic augment also in certain passive simple past forms of learned origin, where it is unstressed

Vocalic Augment:

- the initial V ε-, α-, or αι- of a verb stem is changed ('lengthened') to η- in past tense forms
- limited to a small number of verbs (hardly ever obligatory)
- most common example: ἤ-λπιζα 'I hoped' (imperfect) from ελπίζω, but the unaugmented form ἔλπιζα is also used
- does not normally occur when the initial V does not carry the stress
- also found internally, i.e. after a prepositional prefix

Internal Augment:

- either syllabic or vocalic
- occurs in past tenses of compound verbs, between the prepositional prefix (i.e. prefixes that are derived from Ancient Greek prepositions) and the stem of the verb, and mainly when the stress falls on the augment
- possible prepositional prefixes: αμφι-, ανα-, αντι-, απο-, δια-, εισ-, εκ- (εξ- before a V), εν- (εμ- before β, μ, ν, π, φ, ψ; εγ- before γ, κ, ξ, χ; ελ- before λ), επι-, κατα-, μετα-, παρα-, περι-, προ-, προσ-, συν- (συμ- before β, μ, ν, π, φ, ψ; συγ- before γ, κ, ξ, χ; συλ- before λ; συρ- before ρ; συ- before σ) υπερ-, υπο-
- internal syllabic augment:*
- prepositional prefixes which end in a V (with certain exceptions) drop the final V before an augment (e.g. απο-ρρίπτω 'I reject', simple past: απ-έρριψα)
- exceptions: περι- and προ-, which always retain the V (e.g. περι-πλέκω 'I complicate', s.past: περι-έπλεξα)
- if a prep. prefix has been assimilated to a following C in the present tense, it must be restored to its underlying form when there is a following augment; e.g. συμβαίνει 'it happens' → συν-έβη 'it happened'
- some verbs have two prep. prefixes, e.g. επ-ανα-λαμβάνω 'I repeat' → in such cases the augment comes after the second prefix, e.g. επαν-έλαβα 'I repeated' (-the syllabic augment not obligatory, except when stressed)
- many common verbs with prepositional prefixes never have internal augment, even when it would be stressed
- prefixes other than prepositions which can be combined with a verb include: κακο- 'badly', καλο- 'well', ξανα- 'again', παρα- 'too much, over', πολυ- 'much'
 - after ξανα- and παρα- the use of the stress-carrying augment is optional
 - after the rest of these prefixes the augment is not normally found
- also found in forms with learned endings, particularly in the passive simple past, where it is unstressed (e.g. ανεκοινώθη 'it was announced')

--internal vocalic augment:

- more common in internal position, i.e. after a prepositional prefix, than it is in initial position
- obligatory in the imperfect and simple past of υπάρχω 'I exist' (υπήρχα, υπήρξα)

PARTICLES:

- non-emphatic personal pronouns = unstressed monosyllables → clitics!
- pro- or enclitics are pronounced with stress
- they form a single phonological word with the word which they precede or follow
- enclitics, since they are perceived as forming part of the preceding word, may affect the stress of that word if otherwise the 'three-syllable rule' would be contravened
- thus a word which on its own is proparoxytone receives a stress on its final syllable when followed by an enclitic

→ where two clitics follow a paroxytone, the stress will fall on the first of the clitics

Derivational Morphology:

- formation of new words by means of various morphological processes
- complex words formed by means of either suffixation or prefixation
- formation of compounds (combining the stems of two independent words)

SUFFIXATION:

- vast range of morphological elements which can be added to the stem of a word in order to modify its meaning or to form *derivatives*
- most commonly used suffixes/most productive of new words: *diminutives*, *augmentatives*, *suffixes* to form adjectives or to modify the meaning of existing adjectives, *suffixes* to form nouns

PREFIXATION:

- most commonly used prefixes are words which were prepositions in Ancient Greek, although many of them no longer exist as independent prepositions in the modern language
- some verbs combine two, or even three, of these prepositional prefixes
- prepositional prefixes not restricted to verbs: other parts of speech are formed from such verbs by means of suffixation and other processes (such as a change of a V)
- the prefix ξε- 'un-' never occurs as a preposition on its own
- the prefix α- (αv- before Vs), the so-called *alpha privative* on adjectives to express negation, often stress shift

FORMATION OF COMPOUNDS:

- large number of *compounds* formed from two separate words
- very productively: compounds which are verbs, with the first element related to an adverb
- special type of compounds: the two elements belong to the same part of speech and the resultant word combines the meanings of both; e.g. compounds of two verbs: ανεβοκατεβαίνω 'I go up and down'; compounds of two nouns: αντρόγυνο 'married couple'; compounds of two adjectives: ασπρόμαυρος 'black and white'
- two components of a compound characteristically linked with the V -ο-, e.g. βίος + γράφω → βιογραφία 'biography', γράμμα + σειρά → γραμματσειρά 'character set, font'